

Isolation and Antibigram of Non-Fermentative Gram-Negative Bacilli in Various Clinical Specimens: Implications for Antibiotic Therapy

Vijay Vitore¹, Ahire Gunwant Vijay²

¹Associate Professor, Department of Microbiology, Parbhani Medical College and R.P. Hospital and Research Institute, Parbhani, Maharashtra

²Virologist, Parbhani Medical College RP Hospital and Research Institute

Received: 21-01-2024 Revised: 15-02-2024 / Accepted: 21-03-2024

Corresponding author: Dr. Vijay Vitore

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: A broad class of aerobic, non-spore-forming bacilli known as non-fermentative gram-negative bacilli (NFGNB) either do not use carbohydrates as a source of energy or break them down by alternative metabolic pathways to fermentation. Patients with certain illnesses or conditions are more likely to become infected with non-fermenters. These include cancers, especially those affecting the reticuloendothelial system, instrumentation, surgery, urinary tract catheterizations, intravascular catheterization, lumbar punctures, tracheostomy, dialysis, lavages, shunt placement, prosthetics, prolonged antibiotic use, and chronic infections. Additional risk factors include exudative lesions, burns, and open wounds.

Aim: The study's goal was to identify NFGNB down to the genus and species level and examine their pattern of antibiotic sensitivity and resistance so that the appropriate empirical therapy could be chosen.

Material and Method: The Microbiology Department's Bacteriology Section is where the current study was carried out. Depending on the clinical diagnosis of each patient, a total of 400 clinical samples were taken from patients who were hospitalized to the hospital's ICU and different wards. Urine, pus, blood, ear, high vaginal, sputum, endotracheal secretions, tracheal aspirate, and other bodily fluids were among them. Of the total samples, 250 samples were taken from patients admitted to different hospital wards, and 150 samples were taken from patients in the intensive care unit. In accordance with the guidelines set forth by the institutional ethics committee, each research subject signed an informed consent form. Patients who wished to participate in the trial or their guardians gave written, informed consent.

Results: Non-fermenting Gram-negative bacilli were isolated from 400 clinical specimens accounting for an isolation rate of 10.20%. two fifty specimens (62.5%) showed polymicrobial infection where non-fermenters were isolated along with other organisms, of which *E. coli* and *S. aureus* were commonly associated. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates in our study were highly susceptible to Colistin (96.79%), Amikacin, Tobramycin (75%), Piperacillin/Tazobactam (62.85%) and imipenem (59.61%) Like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter baumannii* was also highly susceptible to Colistin (85.10%). The drug Imipenem in our institute was more sensitive to *Acinetobacter* (75.31%) as compared to *Pseudomonas* (59.61%).

Conclusion: NFGNBs are becoming more and more significant opportunistic pathogens, and they are immune to several conventional antibiotics. Underlying host variables were highly correlated with the result for each of these organisms. Microbiologists and clinics alike have challenges due to the interaction between these multidrug-resistant bacteria and the multidrug-resistant population of immune-compromised patients. Reducing mortality and improving patient management would be achieved by early diagnosis and the implementation of empirical therapy based on the institute's local antibiogram data.

Keywords: Non-fermentative gram-negative bacilli, isolation, antibiogram, antibiotic susceptibility, antibiotic therapy and multidrug resistance.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Groups of rod-shaped, aerobic, non-sporing, gram-negative bacteria are known as non-fermenters. They do not use carbohydrates as a source of energy or break them down through any other metabolic pathway than fermentation. These organisms are commonly thought of as commensals

or contaminants, however due to their frequent isolation from clinical specimens and correlation with the disease, their pathogenic potential has been proven beyond a reasonable doubt. [1] Non-Fermenting Gram-Negative Bacilli (NFGNB) are aerobic, non-sporing bacilli/coccobacilli that either

cannot use carbs as an energy source or break them down by an oxidative process as opposed to a fermentative one. But due to their frequent isolation from clinical specimens and their link to the disease, the pathogenic potential of these organisms has been proven beyond a reasonable doubt. These seemingly disparate bacteria are worthy of research and inclusion in a single group because they share characteristics that are clinically significant. They can be isolated from hospital environments, frequently result in illnesses linked to medical devices, are frequently resistant to disinfectants, and can potentially pass from patient to patient through contact with medical staff or fomites. Furthermore, the NFGNB's antimicrobial resistance provides an epidemiologic niche for these pathogens, which makes it easier for them to colonize and super-infect patients receiving antibiotics. [2-5]

Patients with certain illnesses or conditions are more likely to become infected with non-fermenters. These include cancers, especially those affecting the reticuloendothelial system, instrumentation, surgery, urinary tract catheterizations, intravascular catheterization, lumbar punctures, tracheostomy, dialysis, lavages, shunt placement, prosthetics, prolonged antibiotic use, and chronic infections.

Additional risk factors include exudative lesions, burns, and open wounds. [6] These bacteria almost never cause infections in patients because of predisposing factors like burns, long-term antimicrobial therapy, the use of immunosuppressive medications, advanced age, and the ability of advanced surgical and medical care to prolong a patient's life with multiple severe diseases. [7]

The detection of NFGNBs has long been a laborious operation for a typical microbiological laboratory, and poor laboratory efficiency in this regard is prevalent everywhere, including in our own nation. As a result, there aren't many reports of illness in India caused by these microbes. Commercial kits and automated systems are not always reliable for identification since some BCC strains are mistakenly identified as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, while many non-Burkholderia beta proteobacteria are labeled as BCC. [8]

They are routinely only identified in a small number of Indian laboratories due to their slow growth and the need for specialized culture conditions and biochemical testing. [9-10] Resistance in non-fermenters develops through a variety of mechanisms. Mutations affecting penicillin-binding proteins, efflux pump mechanisms, chromosomal beta-lactamases, and genes encoding porins are among the contributing factors. [11] Understanding the prevalence and

antibiogram of nonfermentive gram-negative bacilli in hospital settings is crucial due to the rising frequency of isolations and the rise in antibiotic resistance. Additionally, the study was conducted to determine the different healthcare-related infections they produce as well as to evaluate their clinical importance and antibiotic susceptibility pattern. Since the selection of antibiotics based on prior knowledge of the agent's susceptibility pattern is crucial to the effectiveness of antimicrobial therapy, this study aimed to identify non-fermenting Gram-negative bacilli isolated from a variety of clinical samples up to the genus and species level as well as investigate their antimicrobial sensitivity and resistance pattern.

Material and Methods

The Microbiology Department's Bacteriology Section is where the current study was carried out. Depending on the clinical diagnosis of each patient, a total of 400 clinical samples were taken from patients who were hospitalized to the hospital's ICU and different wards. Urine, pus, blood, ear, high vaginal, sputum, endotracheal secretions, tracheal aspirate, and other bodily fluids were among them. Of the total samples, 250 samples were taken from patients admitted to different hospital wards, and 150 samples were taken from patients in the intensive care unit. In accordance with the guidelines set forth by the institutional ethics committee, each research subject signed an informed consent form. Patients who wished to participate in the trial or their guardians gave written, informed consent.

Sample Collection:

Every sample was gathered and handled in accordance with accepted microbiological practices. Samples were put under stringent aseptic conditions onto Blood Agar (BA) and MacConkey Agar (MA) plates, and the plates were then incubated at 37°C for 24-48 hours under aerobic conditions. On MacConkey agar media, every organism produced non-lactose fermenting (NLF) colonies. Additionally, growing on triple sugar iron agar and generating an alkaline reaction (K/K) was provisionally regarded as NFGNB.

Gram staining was applied to all isolates that demonstrated non-lactose fermenting colonies on MA and those that developed exclusively on BA and not on MA. Gram-negative bacilli, cocci, and coccobacilli were subsequently exposed to a triple sugar iron test.

Excluded from consideration were the bacterial isolates that exhibited the alkaline/acid (K/A) and acid/acid (A/A) reactions. Provisional isolates were those that generated an alkaline/alkaline (K/K) response. Recognized as non-fermenters, were included in this study, and underwent a battery of

biochemical tests to identify them up to the genus/species level. [12]

Isolate Speciation / Identification:

Following established techniques, traditional biochemical tests were used to identify the clinical isolates. [13] Gram-stain morphology, motility, cytochrome oxidase activity, growth on 10% lactose agar, decarboxylase test, growth on aerobic low peptone medium, triple sugar iron fermentation with hydrogen sulfide production on lead acetate paper, and gelatin liquefaction were among the characteristics evaluated. Numerous tests, including colony characteristics, morphology (Gram's stain), pigment production, motility (by hanging drop), and other biochemical tests, such as the triple sugar iron test, oxidation/fermentation for glucose, lactose, xylose, mannitol, and maltose (Hugh and Leifson's media), Lysine and Ornithine decarboxylase and Arginine dihydrolase activity, ONPG test, Esculin test, etc., were conducted to confirm the isolation of various isolates.

Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing:

Using discs that are readily accessible for purchase (Hi-media), the Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method was utilized to conduct the sensitivity test. Ceftazidime (30 mcg), Ceftriaxone (30 mcg), Cefepime (30 mcg), Imipenem (10µg), Piperacillin-Tazobactam (100/10 mcg), Ticarcillin-Clavulanic acid (75/10 mcg), Ciprofloxacin (5 mcg), Ofloxacin (5 mcg), Amikacin (30 mcg), Gentamycin (10

mcg), Tobramycin (10 mcg), Trimethoprim-Sulfamethoxazole (1.25/23.75 mcg), and Colistin (10 mcg) were among the various antibiotics tested. The Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) criteria were followed in the interpretation of the results. [14]

Following ATCC strains were used as Quality control strains:

ATCC-25922 *E. coli* – Gram-negative bacilli

ATCC-25923 *S. aureus* – Gram-positive cocci

ATCC 27853 *P. aeruginosa*- Non-Lactose Fermenters

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was done by descriptive statistics using the percentages and ratios method.

Result

A total of 500 clinical samples were received from the indoor patients in the microbiology laboratory. Non-fermenting Gram-negative bacilli were isolated from 400 out of 500 clinical specimens accounting for an isolation rate of 10.20%. Two fifty specimens (62.5%) showed polymicrobial infection where non-fermenters were isolated along with other organisms, of which *E. coli* and *S. aureus* were commonly associated. The remaining one-fifty specimens (49.83%) showed monomicrobial infection. The majority of patients (35.13%) belonged to the age group 40-60 years.

Table 1: Microorganisms obtained from different specimens

Organisms	Pus	Urine	Blood	Endotracheal aspirates	CSF	Fluid Aspirates
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	60 74.35%	15 8.01%	10 5.12%	17 6.73%	2 0.96%	11 4.80%
Acinetobacter baumannii	95 45.95%	8 4.25%	30 17.87%	10 5.10%	39 19.14%	15 7.65%
Stenotrophomonas maltophilia	1 13.33%	1 6.66%	5 60.00%	2 20.00%	0 -	0 -
Burkholderia cepacia	1 10.00%	0 -	2 30.00%	3 60.00%	0 -	0 -

Table-1 depicts numbers and percentages of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*, and *Burkholderia cepacia* complex obtained from different specimens.

Table 2: Antimicrobial sensitivity study

Name of Antibiotic	Number and percentage of sensitive <i>Pseudomonas</i> isolates	Number and percentage of Sensitive <i>Burkholderia</i> isolates	Number and percentage of Sensitive <i>Acinetobacter</i> isolates	Number and percentage of Sensitive <i>Stenotrophomonas</i> isolates	Number and percentage of Sensitive <i>Stenotrophomonas</i> isolates
Ceftazidime	95(38.14%)	3(60%)	24(12.34%)	2(26.60%)	2(26.60%)
Ceftriaxone		1(20%)	43(22.12%)	2(20.00%)	2(20.00%)
Cefepime	90(32.05%)	1(10%)	27(13.19%)	1(13.30%)	1(13.30%)
Imipenem	181(59.61%)	1(20%)	168(75.31%)	2(26.60%)	2(26.60%)

Piperacillin/Tazobactam	188(62.85%)	5(60%)	136(60.00%)	5(40.00%)	5(40.00%)
Ticarcillin/Clavulanic Acid	98(33.97%)	3(40%)	132(58.29%)	5(40.00%)	5(40.00%)
Ciprofloxacin	169(56.08%)	4(50%)	47(22.12%)	6(46.60%)	6(46.60%)
Ofloxacin	152(50.00%)	1(10%)	87(39.14%)	4(33.33%)	4(33.33%)
Amikacin	217(75.00%)	3(40%)	89(41.27%)	3(26.60%)	3(26.60%)
Gentamycin	105(37.17%)	1(20%)	37(18.29%)	1(13.30%)	1(13.30%)
Tobramycin	217(75.00%)	1(20%)	99(44.25%)	1(13.30%)	1(13.30%)
Trimethoprim/Sulfamethoxazole	-----	7(80%)	52(25.10%)	8(80%)	8(80%)
Colistin	296(96.79%)	7(80%)	194(85.10%)	12(86.66%)	12(86.66%)

Pseudomonas aeruginosa isolates in our study were highly susceptible to Colistin (96.79%), Amikacin, Tobramycin (75%), Piperacillin/Tazobactam (62.85%) and imipenem (59.61%) Like *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter baumannii* was also highly susceptible to Colistin (85.10%). The drug Imipenem in our institute was more sensitive to *Acinetobacter* (75.31%) as compared to *Pseudomonas* (59.61%).

Discussion

In the past, non-fermenters were typically thought of as pollutants or commensals, but they have now become significant healthcare pathogens. Life-threatening infections like septicemia, pneumonia, urinary tract infections, meningitis, surgical site infections, ventilator-associated pneumonia, osteomyelitis, etc. are linked to these organisms, and treating infections caused by these bacteria has become more challenging due to their resistance to antibiotics. [15] Extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBLs) and metallo-beta-lactamases (MBLs) are known to be produced by NFGNBs, which also have inherent resistance to a variety of antibiotics. [16]

Not fermenting Once thought to be pollutants, gram-negative bacteria are now recognized as significant pathogenic organisms. Various NFGNB isolation rates were reported in earlier investigations. Different workers' investigations have yielded varying outcomes. Mohammad Rahbar et al.2010 [17] and A. Malini et al.2009 [18] reported a positivity rate of 15% whereas Shailpreet Sidhu et al.2010 [19] reported 45.91% of non-fermenters. These variations might be because of the hospital infection control practices of respective institutes. A Malini et al.2009 [18] As with other studies most of the isolates 343 (59.96%) of NFGNB were from pus specimens. The majority of patients had regular use of intrusive devices, such as an endotracheal tube (14.33%), peripheral venous catheter (51.04%), urine catheter (40.03%), and central venous catheter (19.93%). [20]

These patients' devices most likely had the potential to infect them. Costerton JW et al.1999

[21] documented that Biofilm formation by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* plays an important role in the pathogenesis of central venous catheter-related infection, urinary catheter cystitis, contact lens-associated corneal infection, lung infection in cystic fibrosis, and ventilator-associated pneumonia. It was discovered that the most prevalent nosocomial infections were *Acinetobacter* species and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. 95.62% of the isolates were NFGNB, which is a member of the *Pseudomonas* species, and the *Acinetobacter* species. These two species were discovered by additional researchers to be the main pathogen. [22]

The administration of Cotrimoxazole immediately brought a cure in these patients. This is in concordance with the study done by A. Malini et al.2009 [18]; in Kolar, Our study also showed that Fluoroquinolones such as Ciprofloxacin and Ofloxacin are also effective antibiotics against *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* Gilligan PH et al.1991 [23]; reported that the risk factors associated with the acquisition of *Burkholderia cepacia* include older age, more advanced pulmonary disease, and exposure to *Burkholderia cepacia* from previous hospitalization or a sibling with *Burkholderia cepacia* colonization In our study 30% of the isolates of *Burkholderia cepacia* were from old age patients and 40% of the patients gave the history of previous hospitalization.

As concluded by the studies done by Fass RJ et al.1996 [24] Quinn JP1998 [16] and Speert DP2002 [25], *Burkholderia cepacia* complex strains are resistant to most antibiotics commonly used for the treatment of Gram-negative bacterial infections, including the extended-spectrum Penicillins and Aminoglycosides. An additional concerning finding of this study is the high frequency of multi-drug resistance NFGNB.

Notably, due to the high likelihood of these bacteria surviving in hospital settings, measures such as enhanced antibiotic stewardship, hygienic practices, equipment decontamination, stringent hand washing protocols, and isolation protocols must be put in place to stop the emergence and

spread of multidrug-resistant NFGNB in healthcare settings.

Conclusion

NFGNBs are becoming more and more significant opportunistic pathogens and they are immune to several conventional antibiotics. Underlying host variables were highly correlated with the result for each of these organisms. Microbiologists and clinics alike have challenges due to the interaction between these multidrug-resistant bacteria and the multidrug-resistant population of immune-compromised patients. Reducing mortality and improving patient management would be achieved by early diagnosis and the implementation of empirical therapy based on the institute's local antibiogram data. The current study has the capacity to identify species, variables, and antibiotics that influence the course of an infection, which will improve our understanding of these organisms' roles in the development of human disease.

References

- Koneman EW, Winn WC Jr, Allen SD, Janda WM, Procop GW, Schreckenberger PC, Woods GL. Kone-man's color atlas and textbook of diagnostic Microbiology. Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins Company. 2006; 6:303-91.
- Buck AC, Cooke EM; The fate of ingested *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in normal persons. *J Med Microbiol* 1969; 2: 521-25.
- Johanson WG Jr, Higuchi JH, Chaudhuri TR; Bacterial adherence to epithelial cells in bacillary colonization of the respiratory tract. *Am Rev Respir Dis* 1980; 121:55-63.
- Rebecca Reik, Theodore Spilker, John J; LiPuma: Distribution of *Burkholderia cepacia* Complex Species among Isolates Recovered from Persons with or without Cystic Fibrosis. *Journal of Clinical Microbiology* 2005; 43(6): 2926-28.
- Richet H, Escande MC, Marie JP; Epidemic *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* serotype 016 bacteremias in hema-tology-oncology patients. *J Clin Microbiol* 1989; 27: 1992-96.
- Mahon RC, Lehman CD, George M. Non-fermenting and miscellaneous gram-negative bacilli. In: Text-book of Diagnostic Microbiology. 3 rd ed.: New Delhi: Elsevier Publishers; 2006; 564-77.
- Baron EJ, Peterson LR, Finegold SM. Non-fermentative gram negative bacilli and coccobacilli. In: Sha-nahan JF, Potts LM, Murphy C, editors. *Bailey and Scott's Diagnostic Microbiology*. 9 th ed. St. Louis, Missouri: Mosby-Year Book; 1994:386-404.
- Gautam V, Ray P, Vandamme P, Chatterjee SS, Das A, Sharma K, et al.; Identification of lysine positive non-fermenting Gram-negative bacilli (*Stenotrophomonas maltophilia* and *Burkholderia cepacia* com-plex). *Indian Journal of Medical Microbiology* 2009; 27(2):128-133.
- Veenu G, Sikka R, Arora D R. Isolation and susceptibility pattern of non-fermenting gram-negative bacilli from clinical samples. *Int J Med Microbiol*. 1998; 17:14-8.
- Benachinmardi KK, Padmavathy M, Malini J, Navaneeth BV. Prevalence of non-fermenting Gram-negative bacilli and they are in vitro susceptibility patterns at a tertiary care teaching hospital. *J Scientific Society*. 2014; 41:162-66.
- Eltahawy AT, Khalaf RM. Antibiotic resistance among gram-negative non-fermentative bacteria at a teaching hospital in Saudi Arabia. *J Chemotherapy*. 2001;13:260-4.
- Collee JG, Miles RS, Watt B. Tests for identification of bacteria. In: Collee JG, Fraser AG, Marmion BP, Simmons A, editors. *Mackie and McCartney Practical Medical Microbiology*. 14th ed. Singapore: Churchill Livingstone; 2006:131-149.
- Quinn JP; Clinical problems posed by multi-resistant nonfermenting Gram-negative pathogens. *Clin Infect Dis* 1998; 27(1): 117-24.
- Wayne PA; Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. Performance standards for antimicrobial suscepti-bility testing, Fifteenth informational supplement. Approved Standard 2005;7-6.
- Juyal D, Prakash R, Shanakarnarayan SA, Sharma M, Negi V, Sharma N. Prevalence of nonfermenting gram-negative bacilli and their in vitro susceptibility pattern in a tertiary care hospital of Uttarakhand: a study from foothills of Himalayas. *Saudi J Health Sci*. 2013;2:108-12
- Quinn JP. Clinical problems posed by multi-resistant non-fermenting gram-negative pathogens. *Clinical Infectious Dis*. 1998; 27(11):117-24.
- Mohammad Rahbar, Hadi Mehrgan, Negar Haji Ali Akbari; Prevalence of Drug Resistance in Non-fermenter Gram-Negative Bacilli. *Iranian Journal of Pathology* 2010; 15(2).
- Malini A, Deepa EK, Gokul BN, Prasad SR; Nonfermenting Gram-negative bacilli infections in a tertiary care hospital in Kolar, Karnataka. *Journal of lab physicians* 2009; 1(2):62-66.
- Shailpreet Sidhu, Usha Arora, Pushpa Devi; Prevalence of Non-fermentative Gram-Negative Bacilli in Se-riously ill Patients With Bacteraemia. *JK science* 2010; 12(4)

20. Yashodara P, Shyamala S; Identification and characterization of non-fermenters from clinical specimens. *Indian J Med Microbiol* 1997; 15: 195-7
21. Costerton JW, Stewart PS, Greenberg EP; Bacterial biofilms: a common cause of persistent infections. *Science* 1999; 284: 1318–22.
22. Rao PS, Shivananda PG; Bacteraemia due to non-fermenting Gram-negative bacilli in immunocompromised patients. *Int J Med Microbiol* 1993; 11: 95-99.
23. Gilligan PH; Microbiology of airway disease in patients with cystic fibrosis. *Clin Microbiol Rev* 1991; 4: 35–51
24. Fass RJ, Barnishan J, Solomon MC; In vitro activities of Quinolones, β -lactams, Tobramycin, and Trime-thoprim-Sulfa methoxazole against non-fermentative Gram-negative bacilli. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother* 1996; 40: 1412–18.
25. Speert DP; Advances in Burkholderia cepacia complex. *Podiatry Respire Rev* 2002; 3: 230–235.